

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPING THE CREATIVITY OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article describes the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of creativity of future elementary school teachers, as well as the results of the research on the concept of creativity, the meaning and application of the term creativity, and the forms of its manifestation.*

Keywords: *creativity, mathematics, primary education, creative work.*

Introduction

In today's era of globalization, the potential and power of each country can be assessed by the attention paid to education and the development of science in that country. History has also proven that if a country has a strong focus on science, that country will be highly developed. The development of science is the result of the work of mature scientists. President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, "I always try to talk with intelligent, scientific, creative people and I always miss such conversations. Why do you say that science is a great career that shines the light of God? From this career, light and wisdom spread to the whole body of society. From the conversation of scientists, a person gets incomparable spiritual wealth, feels the breadth of the heart, the depth of thinking. They didn't say that for nothing.

In our country, which is moving towards a great future, the issue of personnel and the education of the young generation are among the most urgent issues. However, the future, development and future of Uzbekistan are in the hands of these young people, i.e. the personnel, so it is important for them to be free-thinking, to receive an education that can meet world educational standards, for a great future. It is no exaggeration to say that it is a solid foundation. Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to improve the quality of education in accordance with world standards. In this regard, teaching future primary school teachers to work creatively in mathematics lessons is one of the urgent issues of today.

Literature review

Issues of development of creative qualities and skills Sh.A.Abdullaeva, BRAdizov, A.R.Arifjonova, T.Aliboyev, NNAlimov, GNlbragimova, RFMavlonova, DDMuradova, B.Rakhimov, M.Tilakova, O'.Q.Tolipov Sh. Researched by S. Sharipov, A. Shermuratov, GZYusupova, MMYusupova, K. Kadirov, YA. Kh. Haydarov.

Psychological aspects of the issue of creativity, features of the development of creative abilities in students A.D. Abakumov, N.V.A.Zanova, N.A.Alekseev, O.YU.Aparina, V.I. T. Ermolova, A.Z. Zak, E.P. Ilin, IILyasov, IMKishtomova, S. Krippner VMKozlenko, DMKomsy, Yu.G. Kruglova, PLMeytuv, V.A. Molyako, N.Yu. Postalyuk, SLRubinstein, K It is widely covered in the scientific researches of A. Torshina, BNTeplov, E.I. Sheblanova, VSYurkevich.

Developing Creativity Drapeau Patty, JCGowan, Joyce VanTassel-Baska, Maud Besançon, Miller David Lee, Murat Tekin, RJSternberg, EPTorrance, Ugur Sak, Dj. Gilford, LMTermen, K. Cox, E. Landau, J. Renzullin, F. Barrons researched by

Analysis and results

Creativity is the highest level of human mental activity, freedom, independence, ability to create new and original things. Creative possibilities depend not only on mental ability, but also on the characteristics of certain characters. The development of creative thinking of a person starts from his childhood, and the child wants to be able to demonstrate his existing and unique intelligence, feelings of "I", to attract the attention of others. He is curious about every object and subject. It should be noted that primary school students are distinguished from high school students by their unusual assumptions and unexpected comparisons. This means that the creative ability of future elementary school teachers should be developed at a high level.

Therefore, elementary school students feel the novelty of the mental work offered to them and use their own mental initiative. The student will have to discover many unknown things, look for original, non-standard solutions in various activities. The teacher should be ready for the answers of the students and find suitable solutions for various types of activities. When the time comes, he should think like a child and give unexpected creative answers.

While interpreting creativity as a quality of personality, let's pay attention to the dictionary meaning of this term. This word is derived from the Latin language and means "create"-creative.

To this day, creative concepts and approaches to the development of human culture in different parts of the world; in particular, it has an incomparable place in the development of natural sciences, philosophy, art and humanitarian sciences. Therefore, the ability to think creatively is very different from just random thoughts. Creative thinking is considered a real competence based on knowledge and experience, which allows people to achieve the expected results in tense and complex situations. Societies and organizations around the world are looking at creative thinking and innovative ideas as a shared initiative, focusing on acquiring innovative ideas, knowledge and skills to overcome emerging complexities.

According to Ken Robinson, "creativity is original with its own value a set of ideas". And Gardner in his researches "creativity is a practical action performed by a person, which should reflect a certain novelty and have a known practical value." According to the scientist's approach, creativity means "having a high level of unusual skills along with thorough knowledge of a specific field."

One of the urgent issues facing the future primary school teachers is the formation of creativity in students.

The possibilities of creativity in mathematics lessons and their structural basis are as follows:

Depth of thought - the number of ideas that arise in a certain time unit;

Flexibility of thought is the ability to switch from one thought to another.

The originality of thought is the ability to respond to stimuli in a non-standard way.

Curiosity, intelligence - sensitivity to contradictions and uncertainties, readiness to quickly switch from one idea to another.

The ability to draw quick conclusions is a clear idea that needs to be carefully checked later.

Summary - the result of creativity, the logical independence of reactions from stimuli, the ability to solve problems, analyze and synthesize.

In order to develop creativity in mathematics classes, future teachers should first of all develop their own thinking in different directions, analyze the problematic situation in different ways, find the optimal solution in unusual situations, and develop their own mental activity. A gifted person is considered another form of ability - creative ability. The qualities characteristic of a person with creative abilities are: observation, strength of memory, formation of visual imagination, creativity (creativity), independent thinking, initiative, the desire to create innovations, inquisitiveness, critical self-evaluation, richness of fantasy, the simplest elements also progress.

In order to develop his creative abilities, a person should constantly read works of art, get acquainted with examples of theater, cinema, music, visual arts and handicrafts, and enjoy various works of art, and form his own opinion about them.

Many studies conducted in pedagogical, psychological and philosophical directions show that creative activity is organized by a person in several stages. In particular, the English scientist G. Wallace in 1924 stated that this process consists of four stages, and they are as follows:

- preparation process;
- the process of the birth of ideas;
- the process of their full reflection;
- inspection (control) process.

Conclusions and recommendations

Creativity (creativity) is an integral aspect of the activity of a person with creative and creative abilities, and it represents the creation of new things based on the qualities that did not exist before. According to the manifestation and result of creative ability: it also reflects the content of activity with unique, originality and socio-historical character. The qualities of creativity (creativity) in a person develop only when there are certain conditions and conditions. For example, freedom of criticism, creative discussion, exchange of ideas and mutual struggle between them, helps to further develop creative ability and talent.

In my opinion, by forming creative thinking in elementary school students, the teacher guarantees that students will independently complete educational tasks, find ways to solve problems, and develop their own personal relationships in various situations.

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